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Lean accreditations

Anne-Marie JOLLY

CTI (Commission des Titres d'Ingénieur)
Polytech Orléans
Paris, France

E-mail: anne-marie.jolly@cti-commission.fr

Christine FREYERMUTH

CTI (Commission des Titres d'Ingénieur)
Paris, France

E-mail: christine.freyermuth@cti-commission.fr

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INTRODUCTION

Quality assurance and accreditation agencies are developing for many years: in France engineering education institutions are accredited by Commission des Titres d'Ingénieur (CTI) since 1934, and many agencies have already done several cycles of their periodic evaluation in the institutions. Very often, the deans of those evaluated institutions say that it is not possible to continue because, together with their team, they spend huge amounts of time writing self-evaluation reports or preparing audits, instead of making their institutions evolve. These two activities are really very time consuming for institutions.

On the other hand, the human cost of evaluation is very high for auditors too, and much time is also spent by evaluators reading the same documents as in the previous audit or visiting institutions that have not really changed, and then writing and presenting the results of those investigations.

Everywhere in the world there are reflexions or attempts to make those accreditations lighter, some have not yet results such as in HFKG (Federal Council of Switzerland) [1]. We will limit our presentation to the French speaking countries that are Belgium and France where this new process is beginning in October 2018.

In 2017, it was decided to launch a reflexion on a leaner accreditation process; this took place in CTI nearly at the same time as Belgium AEQES (Agence pour l'évaluation de la qualité de l'enseignement supérieur) began to have ideas of the same kind. Nowadays HCERES (Haut Conseil de l'évaluation de la recherche et de l'enseignement) which is our generalist agency is also having a reflexion on those fields for private institutions, it is called "audit adaptés" which means fitted audits, this process changes only the duration of audits but not the SER of institutions.

It took many meetings in CTI to define what was really important to be observed and understood in institutions when they were accredited; this common reflexion, where external experts contributed, was in itself a result for the CTI. We first got to a common view on the necessary elements that make us think that a complete accreditation process is not necessary and then we established the documents necessary for this lean accreditation, the organisation of audit itself being also fitted to this new process. The paper presents the step and conclusions of this work done inside CTI as well as some elements of the work done on Belgium on the same subject, because it is interesting to compare these approaches for two reasons: first one is that AEQES is our French speaking neighbour but also because we have common accreditation procedures in Belgium institutions, so CTI's members will have to participate to a lean accreditation experimentation different from what has been decided in France. Concepts underlying the two demarches are different, which gives richness to this double participation, we present will this paper in a way that we discuss this point.

1 THE CONTEXT

1.1 The situation resulting from periodic accreditation

In France as well as in French speaking Belgium, periodic accreditation takes place each 5 years. In France, in most of engineering education institutions both HCERES which is the French generalist evaluation agency and CTI which is the engineering education agency come each five years because the contract that the ministry of higher education sign with those institutions is renewed every 5 years. For the time being HCERES and CTI are trying to synchronize their evaluation for some institutions (same self-evaluation report, same sequences shared during the audit), however it is impossible to do so for all institutions because of problems of synchronisms of annual agendas of agencies.

ENQA (European Association for Quality assurance in Higher Education) asks its agencies members to consult very regularly stakeholders and to take into account, if possible, their opinion on the evaluation processes and its criteria. Concerning French Deans it was clear from our discussions that several of them were fed up with all the time spent for preparing twice documents each 5 years, however, we saw in the afterward reactions that things are not so simple.

In Belgium, things were of the same nature, accreditation taking place each 5 years too, AEQES edits after each campaign on a specific field of education, a transversal analysis on this field; each institution can read it and this gives indications on the trend of the subjects more often questioned during evaluation, making them reflect on the subjects.

We do not realise this transversal analysis in France but each year CTI publishes the statistics on recommendations and on strengths of institutions accredited during that year [5], this document does not indicate which institution is concerned with each item but it gives a good global information to the schools that want to progress: we can notice that periodic accreditation made institutions really progress; the accreditation agency visiting the school

each 5 year, since 1997, with different experts which insures a different look, even on the same criteria, analysis of weaknesses shows that the main weakness of schools stays the quality system of the institution. This explains the importance given to quality system in the criteria for lean audits.

1.2 The vision of AEQES of follow up audits

AEQES at the contrary now makes a distinction in the aims between 2 consequent periodic evaluations [2] it is not the only agency to do so, but if we observe what ACEEU (Accreditation council for entrepreneurial and engaged universities) proposes [3] in its reaccreditation process, we can see that few changes occur (fig 1) while in AEQES all the process is completely revisited (fig 2).

Figure 1

The first evaluation of AEQES is aimed at inviting the institution to have a look on itself and make a deep self-evaluation of its programmes, while the external experts make recommendations useful to improve their quality. Based on AEQES quality standards, this evaluation includes 3 steps:

- self-evaluation of the institution
- external evaluation realized through an expert committee, this step including a site visit and publication of the evaluation report
- publication of an action plan elaborated by the institution and its implementation

The agency then publishes a transversal analysis of the global quality of evaluated curricula.

The second one called “follow up evaluation”, is a lean evaluation and has the aim of supporting institutions in their continuous improvement dynamic, in the development of the actions presented in the action plan and in the construction of tools helping the governance.

So, a follow up evaluation considered as a consolidation evaluation, it is composed of 3 steps:

- a progress assessment of the actions already done
- an audit realised by a pool of experts, writing a public report
- the publication by the institution of an action plan and its implementation

AEQES thinks that evaluation cannot be limited to a diagnostic, it must also support the institutions for action: this explains and justifies the follow up phase. In this way it becomes much more than a strict external evaluation, because it becomes the concrete implementation of the quality policy of the institution. We can put this concept in parallel with the formative evaluation of our students because the same process is in action. While discussing with institutions we understood that more than the evaluation report it is self-evaluation that makes institutions progress [4]: the quality policy of the institution, leading to the construction of an actualised action plan, and its follow up is of the first importance.

The evaluation report itself allows the institution to confront the self-analysis of the institution to an external vision, thanks to the recommendations enunciated by the committee: so it can bring the institution a support to adjust the action plan that self-evaluation had helped to construct. ENQA in ESG 1.9 makes mandatory the publication of the action plan of the institution, so, AEQES asks that 6 months after the publication of the evaluation report of the experts, the institution publishes its actualised action plan on its website. The efforts made to really follow the plan, which are evaluated during the follow up evaluation, attest the wish of institution for continuous improvement inside a culture of integrated quality.

Figure 2

The aim of follow up audits is to support institutions in their dynamic for continuous improvement, in the pursuit of the actions already engaged and in the development of tools for quality. So, this audit at half course of a decadal cycle of evaluation maintains a true engagement towards quality because it intends to measure both the ability of the institution to change and the culture of quality.

The monitoring file elaborated by the institution for this follow up audit is not a complete self-evaluation report it only includes an introduction, a state of realizations with an analysis and annexes. In the introduction, the institution can explain the changes in the governance and in the program that happened since the previous evaluation. In the part where the institution presents the state of realisation of its initially planned actions, the institution also presents the actions it wishes to realize so as to improve the quality of its training offer. The questions raised in this part are:

-Since the previous evaluation, in the implementation of the action plan, which are the two or three more significant advances?

-Which are the two or three greatest difficulties encountered?

-Which is the retrospective look on the operating modes of the institution and how the stakeholders have been involved in the implementation of the action plan?

-Which are the two or three more priority actions for the next months or years?

In the annexes the institution gives the previous recommendations and their follow up, the initial action plan, a SWOT analysis, and an action plan actualized.

As a conclusion we can say that this vision of lean accreditation is very efficient in helping institutions in their approach of progress: as AEQES has not the mission of accreditation in its statute, this is a good way of proceeding for evaluation; on the contrary, CTI has an accreditation to decide each five years, so the way of operating is different, though the objective of improving the quality of the institutions is common to both agencies.

1.3 Vision of French accreditation agency on lean accreditation

The CTI is in a position where it is at the same time conscious of the weight of this accreditation for institutions and, as a representing of the French Minister and of the whole society (engineers, future engineers and employers) of the necessity of a control. Its position is then a mix between the evaluation of quality structures of the institution and the verification that CTI's criteria have really been taken into account.

Each 10 years, institutions have to go through a complete process of accreditation but the accreditation that institution has in between will not necessarily be a lean accreditation. So, a synchronisation will not exist between normal and lean accreditations of all institutions as in Belgium. The first thing necessary to elaborate were the conditions that the institution should meet so that a lean accreditation could take place: our first step was the definition of those criteria.

2 CRITERIA LEADING CTI TO THINK THAT A LEAN AUDIT IS POSSIBLE

At the beginning of the reflexion of CTI, the problem of audits arriving far in advance (3 years instead of 5) in the agenda, because of the synchronisation with the signature of the minister's contract, made us imagine a lighter audit than usual for those institutions; but, when we decided to extend this process to other institutions, it was necessary to describe the criteria that the institutions that would benefit from a leaner audit must meet.

The general information is that the institution must not have encountered major problems. It can be divided into two characteristics, one concerning the history of the institution: previous durations of the accreditation and previous recommendations and the other one concerning the quality system of the institution.

2.1 The quality of institution

Quality of institutions should be at the heart of the process of evaluation. However, in France, when we make the statistics of the recommendations given to institutions during the year, the

recommendation that arrives first in order in about half of the institutions is “to put in place a quality system “[5]

This shows that in France, for the time being, the culture of quality is not evident in institutions and that progresses have still to take place. CTI has a part to play for the development of those quality processes. This criterion is in a way very near to the AEQES one: if an institution is able to develop a good policy for its quality, CTI can trust it and let it have lighter accreditation, but the institution has also to be supported in this process through the leaner accreditation.

2.2 Level of satisfaction of the previous evaluation of the institution: duration and recommendations

At the end of each accreditation process, CTI gives or not an accreditation that can be either for 5 years (best result), 3 years (things that can be improved) or 1 year if CTI thinks that the program must be closed: it is possible to go to a lean accreditation only if the program has had a duration of 5 years' accreditation. This accreditation is given together with recommendations that the institution has to follow until the next accreditation time, so the second characteristic is the kind of recommendations given to this institution in the previous evaluation.

In CTI we have major criteria concerning several fields of the institution [6]. These fields are:

A Mission and organization of the institution in its context, B Partnerships of the institution, C The process of education of students, D Recruitment of students, E Employment of graduates, F Quality processes and continuous improvement

The recommendations after an audit can be given on any of these criteria. So CTI had to debate on the importance of these recommendations to decide if an institution can benefit from a lean audit.

As a conclusion, we see that the approach of lean audit is significantly different between France and Belgium: in one country all the institutions will benefit of a lean audit, at the contrary in France only “good pupils” can benefit from it: this difference is linked to two different dimensions: the culture of quality being more present in Belgium than in France for the time being, the second one being the fact that AEQES makes evaluation while CTI realises accreditation.

3 SELF ASSESSMENT DOCUMENT AND CRITERIA ASSOCIATED

When the institutions being relevant from a lean accreditation process have been stated by the Commission, they are advised that they will have to realise a shorter document (maximum 20 pages) based on elements decided by the CTI [7]. It is important to recall that even in those circumstances the frame of reference is always the same (R & O Volume 1) [6] but only the description of some parts is needed and the auditors will focus their observations on those parts.

3.1 The free part of the document

The institution knows its own contexts, it is important that it can express and explain positions concerning its evolutions. The institution has to develop in its document the internal evolution or the contextual evolutions that it had to live since the previous audit. So it can choose and develop these elements freely.

3.2 The mandatory items that must be developed in the SER

As CTI is an accreditation agency, some accreditation criteria have more importance than other, and some others can be new ones, so CTI asks the institution to develop on those points. First one is the complete description of the field of criteria that concerns its quality approach and its process of continuous improvement. CTI particularly asks to develop this field in reference to the ESG 2015 [8] edited by ENQA.

The criteria newly introduced (R &O changed in 2016) must be developed, they concern:

- the importance of fundamental and applied research in curricula
- the education to entrepreneurship and innovation
- the practice of another foreign language than English one
- the outgoing and ingoing mobility that must be followed by a return on experience with the students concerned
- the teaching and projects on sustainable development, social responsibility of companies, ethics and deontology: they have been introduced recently by CTI, some institutions have not been evaluated since this time
- the fundamental skill basis described for the program must be insured whatever the minors chosen by the student are
- there is a clear process established for the treatment of appeals in the institution
- any student can realize a one year break of study during at most one year but this must respect the terms of French law

The other elements are linked to institutional stakes, necessary check points on education, and new legal dispositions. They can concern as well site policy, pedagogic innovation, diversity, double diploma, contracts of professionalization, validation of the student commitment. It must be noticed that these two parts represent 15 on the 20 pages of the file (for an institution that has only a program to be accredited), the remaining of the file being constituted of mandatory parts such as data on the school or the note of strategic evolution of the institution.

4 THE FIRST RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

For the moment this new procedure has been presented and explained both to institutions and to auditors. As for each new process many questions arise and no doubt that some documents will have to be improved or more defined for the next campaign according to the quality policy of CTI (yearly surveys of institutions and auditors are realised)

However, the choice of this strategy for lean audit is perfectly assumed by CTI, it can give a model for other agencies that are having a reflexion at the same moment, either on their policy, either on the link between internal and external quality process, in this sense the comparison with the choice made by AEQES is interesting because this choice delegates to the institution a greater responsibility. Opportunities are also given to the institution to develop a portfolio [8] if they wish to, this new possibility can make our process evolve, but this supposes that the institution has an information system rather elaborated, which is not the case in all institutions for the moment.

All these changes are not so evident and many questions arise as well for schools as from auditors: CTI is in the process of changing and it is not evident for itself as well as for its stakeholders. For example, some drawbacks are possible because of lack of a complete vision of the commission on the institution and its historic. Our debates could be a bit different from what they are now, a strong recommendation to members to read the previous accreditation reports has to be made.

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